

The Investigating Into the Relative Importance of Toxic Leadership Dimensions in Appearance of Preventive Stress at Work in Post Office of Ardabil Province.

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Abstract

This study is about "the investigating into the relative importance of toxic leadership dimensions in appearance of preventive stress at work in post office of Ardabil province" by using descriptive-correlation method. Thus, offensive leadership relationship, imperative leadership, narcissistic leadership, self-promoting leadership, unpredictable leadership had studied as main categories with preventive stress at work. The present study has been performed in two section of theoretical and practical. In theoretical section, necessary data had been collected by using library and attributive method, and in practical method, necessary data had been collected by field method by a questionnaire of statistical samples (136 people of Ardabil province post office staffs). Analyzing data by using Pearson correlation coefficients indicate that there is a significant positive relationship between toxic leadership dimensions in appearance of preventive stress at work.

Key words: toxic leadership, preventive stress at work, self-promoting leadership, imperative leadership.

Introduction

Leadership is the ability of influence on a group in order to achieving an aim or specified aims (Robbins, 1997: 85). And leadership style is permanent and constant behavior patterns that people use it in working with others and it perceives by people (Moghimi, 2011: 28). Totally, leadership is the derivation of effectiveness on actions of a person or a group that they attempt in a determined situation towards achieving an aim. It is included that leadership process is a function of leader variations, follower and other situation variations. From the view point of theoretical and also experimental, it is seemed that the relationship between leader and his/her group members is the important variation in determining his/her power and influence. Experimental studies confirm this hypothesis (Moshabbaki, 1998). That is, it can be said that leadership isn't confined to influence that a person acts in a special role, but followers are a part of leadership process and relationship between leader and his/her followers has been emphasized by social and management sciences scholars. Also, Likert shows that skilled manager emphasizes on a good relationship in order to cooperation with subordinates (Venter, 2001).

Management pattern and model in every society has been influenced by leadership methods. Some researchers believe that the main difference between a successful organization and unsuccessful organizations is the leadership method. Leadership is a central point of scholar researchers during various decades and there have been write thousands research articles about this subject. Some studies have been attempted that study habits, behaviors and methods that are relative with a successful leadership. Some of them have been attempted that study nature and results of unusual leadership (Ashfort et al, 2002). In general, it can be categorized management and leadership methods into the three sections: autocratic method, control and arbitration method, and magnanimously method. Some knowledgeable believe that the management leadership style is influenced by his/her view towards his self/herself role and employers and also how manger's behaviors and decides can influenced on motivation and job's satisfaction of employers (Hendi, Quoted from Mokhber, 1996).

For long years, leadership theories had been focused on its positive aspect and this is led to a positive dogmatism (politir and rotir, 2011). Thus, we want to provide beliefs about leadership phenomenon by using review of literature, studies and the present references in this field and administrative experiments of authors that there has been little research's about it. Really, our aim is eliminating positive paradigm inadequacies towards leadership. Then, we are going to review behavioral characteristics and some toxic leader's characteristics. A bad leadership can be has negative effects on organization and its members and also it can be harmful for follower's health (politir, 2009). Researchers have suggested a range of bad and inappropriate leadership about aspects of charisma and offensive management, cruel, destructive, racketeer, narcissist, ineffective and immortal and toxic leadership. These studies present a special composition of negative qualities and it is called toxic leadership, because they suppose that this leadership style has negative results for subordinates and organization. Toxic leadership has been paid attention to organizations, for example, United States military has emphasized the necessary for definition and conception of toxic leadership. Red writers that in 2003, Tomas Ewhite that he was the military's secretary, wanted to show his that how military can find leaders that they may have destructive leadership method (Rotir, 2011: 67).

Although, the mentioned publications have been done primary attempts for conception of this structure, they don't have experimental support for their claims and everyone has his/herself definition of toxic leadership. Thus, the first step in conception of this structure is the general definition of toxic leadership. If this duty is very difficult in order to the word of "toxic" is used for description of unusual leaders, for example, there is a list of toxic leaders (Lipman and

Blueman, 2005) that they are politicians that they govern within their country and their inside cycle by information control and the instillation of fear and terror, an administrative manager leads to company's bankruptcy by a collection of bad business decisions, clearly, leadership and individual qualities are very valuable and still they are within the definition of toxic leadership for Lipman and Blueman leadership. Other sample is Viker categorization (1998) of effectiveness leadership, this categorization shows the similar disarray, although, it is caused a fine separation by breaking toxic leadership in toxic and transitional categories. Even types of toxic leadership indicate many variations in toxic rate. Some writers use "toxic leadership" for describing people that they use it in leadership placement that they have detectable clinical mental disorder (Goldman, 2006). During recent decades, with becoming more complex job categories and human relationship and job's environments, there has been discussed job's stress. Job's stress can be known as any harmful mental-physical response that it is resulted from lack of person's ability with job's environment. This response can be has a direct relative with job's satisfaction and individual's performance as dissatisfied behaviors, being struggle in harsh behaviors, job's accident and injury, various physical diseases and even death and low appearance of job's stress, and it is one of the effective components of individual's health, safe and comfort (James, 2008: 124).

The aim of author in this research is leadership and management's exploitation from results of this research in post office organization for improvement of organization's condition for advancement of organization's goals. Thus, what is leadership style's condition in organization in the statistical population? What is job's stress? According to these questions, which are methods of helping to organization for advancement of suitable leadership and reducing job's stress? In general, the main aim of this study is that what relationship is there between toxic leadership dimensions in appearance of preventive stress at work among post office staffs of Ardabil province?

Theoretical principles

Toxic leadership

Toxic leadership refers to a process that leaders cause serious harms for subordinates and others by destructive behaviors and by ineffective characteristic qualities. Toxic leaders are commanders that they prioritize their benefits, subordinates are under surveillance meticulously and they are weak in the process of making decisions. Toxic leaders work for their promotion and they do their acts without considering long-term results for subordinates, unit and organization. These leaders consider very intelligent their self and always reprove staffs and they stalls on the answering to questions about leadership style. The definition of toxic leadership is according to basis of subordinate's perceptions and if subordinates are sustained harms from leader's acts, thus leader is a toxic leader (Hepel, 2011).

According to Lipman, these leaders don't act similarly, they may be effectiveness in some situations, also people's views towards them are different and sometime leadership maybe toxic from the view point of someone and it maybe called strongman from the view point of other someone (Lipman and Blueman, 2005).

Characteristics of toxic leaders

1. They often make decisions hastily and they suddenly change guidelines routing without any rational reason.
2. They motivate by their self benefits.
3. They are proud of their job's domain.
4. Instead of developing staffs, they are fighting with them, and staffs are under severe controls from them.
5. They focus on short-term successes.
6. They overthrow others for their successes.

Personality traits of toxic leaders

1. over ambition
2. Megalomania as they can't see their defects.
3. Pride that it is an obstacle for considering mistakes.
4. Greed and rapacity.
5. Chicken-hearted that they evade from adapting decisions.
6. They are weak in perception of problems.
7. Lack of ability for recognition of good and bad (Roter, 2011).

"Lipman-Blueman" believe that toxic leadership includes behaviors as following: humiliation and derision, weakening of morale, less attention towards followers, forcing with threat, deception, intentional destruction, elimination of people and competitors, putting Members against each other, kicking of social group, deprived of social rights and electoral right, encouragement of staffs for reprimand of each other, partisanship, aggression, physical act, threat of staffs for end of duty, force of people for tolerance of hardship, blame of followers for their mistakes, ignoring suggestions, revolting in the bud of contrary's view, being not available the required information for staffs or hate ideology promotion of co-worker, causing division and even jailing, tormenting or killing people.

Stress and jobs stressors

Stress is a situation that it is caused by various physiological-mental variations on two factors of job and physical health and personal feeling that it is a set of public and individuals responses towards incompatible and unpredictable elements of environment that it is led to disorder in adaptation system and forced him to adopting escape or war

method to deal with risk or dispose of it. New investigations and comprehensive theories about stress focus on individual and environmental interaction and individual's response against stress depends to awareness and unawareness evaluation and representation, the importance of harmful events (Dayer, 2001). Although, stress is defined as various forms, but the similar field of all definitions is that the reason of causing stress is the existing of a stimulus as physical or mental and individual responses to it by a special method. In this discussion, stress considered as an individual's response for adaptation towards a stimulus that it is caused physical and mental necessities for his/her that he/she adapts his/her with mental stress conditions and stimuli are the reason of physical or mental stress that he/she feels that he/she hasn't ability for doing works (Griffin, 1985: 45). Thus, stress is one of the social and organizational phenomenons that organizational space, human relations and their mental health is influenced by it (Feghhi Farahmand, 2002: 542). Although, some experts believe that mental stress isn't destructive, but some researchers believe that mental pressure is disruptive of mental health and it is one of the manager's problems that it is reduced efficiency and productivity and it is caused behavioral problems and contradiction among organizations and it is investigable in every aspects of organization such as physical conditions, type of work, responsibility, evaluation, structure, role, type of characteristic, process of production, communication, etc.

Research method

A) Research method: This study is a correlation study for the purpose of practical aim and in view of conduct the research, it is descriptive survey.

B) Statistical population: Statistical populations of this research are all staffs of Ardabil province post office that they are 220 people.

c) Sample volume and sampling methods: sampling is a collection of acts. The used method for sampling is simple accident method that according to Morgan Table, number of statistical samples is 136.

D) Measurement tools and collecting data: Field data collection had been done using questionnaire. There has been used for collecting data from two questionnaires:

- A questionnaire that it is included dedicated questions about toxic management that there have been selected and designed 20 questions about independent variables with regard to studied components in this research.

Third section: It is included dedicated questions about job's stress that has been selected and designed 20 questions about dependent variable.

H) Reliability and Validity: The order of validity is that the measurement tool can measure considered question. For determining content validity, a questionnaire was given to some experts and some management and behavioral science professors and it had been consulted about questions and evaluation of hypothesis and validity of questionnaire had been approved and reliability of questionnaire calculated with coefficient of Cronbach alpha in this research for dependant variable and for each of independent variables, and their alpha was more than 87%.

I) Data analyzing method: In this research, there has been used from SPSS software for exploitation of information and their analyzing.

Findings

The main hypothesis: There is a relationship between toxic leadership dimensions and appearance of preventive stress at work.

Table 1: Results of Pearson correlation coefficient between toxic leadership with appearance of preventive stress at work

	Statistics	appearance of preventive stress at work
Toxic leadership	correlation coefficient	0.227
	Significant level	0.008
Offensive leadership	correlation coefficient	0.229
	Significant level	0.007
Imperative leadership	correlation coefficient	0.552
	Significant level	0.001
Narcissistic leadership	correlation coefficient	0.429
	Significant level	0.001
Self promoting leadership	correlation coefficient	0.780
	Significant level	0.000
Unpredictable leadership	correlation coefficient	0.453
	Significant level	0.000

According to table 1 and with regard to this that significant level of test error for reliability level 95% is less than 5%, thus it can be said that first hypothesis to sixth and there is a significant relationship between all toxic leadership dimensions with appearance of preventive stress at work. Also, correlation coefficient was between toxic leadership

22%, offensive leadership 22%, imperative leadership 55%, narcissistic leadership 42%, and self promoting leadership 78%, unpredictable leadership 45% with appearance of preventive stress at work.

There has been used from relative importance technique for providing effect of toxic leadership elements on appearance of preventive stress at work and also the net effect and weight. In following table, there has been determined relative importance of each toxic leadership elements:

Table 2: relative importance of toxic leadership dimensions on the appearance of preventive stress at work

Dimensions of toxic leadership	The crude weight of each variable	The relative weight of each variable from 100%	The number of participants
Offensive leadership	0.065	7.8%	136
Imperative leadership	0.145	17.4%	
Narcissistic leadership	0.089	10.6%	
Self promoting leadership	0.427	51.1%	
Unpredictable leadership	0.110	13.2%	
Total	R2=0.837	100%	

The relative importance method indicates that in toxic leadership, the effect of toxic leadership dimensions is 83 percent. From this 83 percent, 42 percent of it (approximately 51 relative weights) belongs to self promoting leadership.

Discussion and conclusion

Organizations require fast adaptation with variations in order to achieving competitive position with international arena and organizations must be have leaders and staffs that they are adaptable and they work effectively, they improve systems and processes and they are customer-oriented. Thus, it is necessary that we must be having leaders that they can perform wisely that final aim of this case is assurance of organizational successfulness and optimal performance in global market. Leadership is that leader has the ability for penetration on a group in order to achieving aim or determined aims (Robbinz, 1997: 85) and leadership style is permanent behavioral patterns that people use from it by others and it perceives by others (Moghimi, 2011: 28). The results of present study indicate that there is a relationship between toxic leadership dimensions (offensive leadership, imperative leadership, narcissistic leadership, self promoting leadership and unpredictable leadership) and appearance of preventive stress at work. And also results of relative importance method showed that in toxic leadership, the dimensions of toxic leadership are effective about 83 percent. From this 83 percent, 42 percent of it (about 51 percent of relative weight) belongs to self promoting leadership.

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